

Student Preference and Perception towards Online Education in Hyderabad City

Mr. Anjum Pasha¹, Jarupla Gorya²

¹Lecturer in Management Studies, ²Student

^{1,2}JNTUH College of Engineering, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

How to cite this paper: Mr. Anjum Pasha | Jarupla Gorya "Student Preference and Perception towards Online Education in Hyderabad City" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3 , April 2019, pp.656-659, URL: <http://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd22876.pdf>

IJTSRD22876

ABSTRACT

The purpose of study an online education industry in its totality and appreciate the use of an integrated approach in understanding the environmental issues and problems. From the last few years the technological advancement and increased users of internet made everything's easier for everyone. If you want to purchase anything you will access online Shopping sites and order product to get at your hand. Whereas new way of getting education is online education/ virtual education/ E-learning. Like shopping sites, internet also made easier to get education via online. This is really made easy for those who want to work as well as study further. In this report I compared both online education and traditional way of education. We also listed out top 10 international educational sites as well as top 5 Indian online educational sites.

KEYWORDS: E-learning, online education, Student

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

INTRODUCTION ABOUT EDUCATION:

Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. Educational methods include storytelling, discussion, teaching, training and direct research. Training activities often take place under the guidance of educators, but students can also educate themselves. Education can take place in a formal or informal context, and any experience that has educational efficacy in the way one thinks, feels or acts can be considered educational. The teaching methodology is called pedagogy.

In general, education is formally divided into phases, such as kindergarten or kindergarten, primary school, high school and then university, university or apprenticeship. The right to education has been recognized by some governments and the United Nations. In most regions, education is mandatory until a certain age.

Online education is a type of educational instruction that is delivered via the internet to students using their home computers. During the last decade, online degrees and courses have become popular alternative for a wide range of non-traditional student's, include those who want to continue working full-time or raising families. Most of the time, online degree programs and courses are offered via the

host school's online learning platform, although some are delivered using alternative technologies. Although there are subtle dissimilarities, the main difference between online and traditional learning is the fact that online education liberates the student from the usual trappings of on-campus degree programs — including driving to school, planning their schedule around classes, and being physically present for each sequence of their coursework. If this sounds drastic, it really isn't. The truth is, the education methods and materials provided in online degree programs are often the same as those provided for on-campus programs. According to Robert Monroe, Director of the Online Hybrid MBA at Carnegie Mellon University's Tepper School of Business, the best online education programs actually mirror their on-campus equivalent.

ONLINE EDUCATION TYPES:

Online courses: even if online courses can be part of a degree course, they can be carried out independently to master a particular subject or learn a specific skill. Hybrid education: hybrid education allows students to follow a combination of courses online and on campus.

Regardless of the type or types of online training you choose, the options are generally abundant. Where online education

has taken root in a handful of college students, it has since expanded to almost all academic fields and disciplines, with very few exceptions. That said, some fields lend themselves to online learning for several reasons.

Across the country, the most popular degree programs offered online include:

- Computer and Information Technology
- Accounting
- Criminal Justice
- Business Administration
- Nursing

BENEFITS OF ONLINE EDUCATION:

The benefits that come from online learning depend very much on the individual. While some students simply enjoy the convenience of studying in their pajamas, others must choose online education to stay home with their children. Even so, the biggest advantage that comes with online degree programs has to do with location. Simply put, when you're engaged in online education, you don't have to uproots, staying at home to get a degree not only allows you to get a degree, but also takes less time. For example, students studying online may not have to do so

"The main advantage of an online program is flexibility," says Monroe. "In a well-designed online program, students are not limited to programs physically located near their home."

- They left work to go to school.
- Travel to and from your university campus.
- Plan your day around your course schedule.
- Spend money in the parking lot or in childcare.

To reduce the impact, many online schools have started to offer a wide range of services that connect students with their colleagues and instructors. Commonly, these features include online message boards and chat rooms, video conferencing and web-based forums:

"The main advantage of a campus-based program, compared to an online program, is the opportunity it offers for personal interactions with their teachers and colleagues," says Monroe. "For many, learning is basically a social activity and these person-to-person interactions are a very important component of their education." Of course, nothing is perfect, and while there are many advantages, online education has one drawback: the lack of a personal connection. At the same time, it allows them to study and take exams at the time and place that best suits them, learn at their own pace and move their courses faster.

NEED OF STUDY:

Online education in India has seen a rapid progress in the recent times, making it one of the most discussed subject in the education domain.

Students now have access to the best courses from all around the globe to be skilled in these domains. A number of renowned universities are now offering online distance education, bringing world class instructors and professors to educate the students.

SCOPE OF STUDY:

The geographical scope of study is confined to the city of Hyderabad. This is based on questionnaire to find out their customer perception towards online education the various elements.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To know most preferred way of education.
2. To know why people preferring online education over offline education.
3. To Study the opinion of students, teachers and parents regarding online education.
4. To know the future scope of online education.
5. To know advantages and disadvantages of online and offline education.
6. To know why people don't prefer online education.
7. To know whether it will be treated as same as offline education or not.

LIMITATIONS:

1. The study is only applicable to the Hyderabad city.
2. The study is done on the basis of the data provided by the respondents.
3. The questionnaire is designed based on our research objectives.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Reddy et al. (2001)

conducted a study on students experience with virtual campus. The objective of this survey study was to analyze the attitude of the learners towards resource-based learning and to critically examine the utilization of the resources provided by the university; and to suggest measures for improving the effectiveness of resource-based learning. The questionnaire that was mainly structured with a few close-ended (objective type) and open-ended questions was sent to the students of various tele-centers. Out of 1266 learners, 443 (35%) have returned the filled in questionnaires. Around ¾ of the respondents replied positively. Majority (68%) of them felt that they could construct their own individual knowledge base; 60% of them liked the flexibility in study routes; 46% improved their study skills; 29% could think more; 28 % found it interesting and stimulating; 42% enjoyed the independence, and 29% liked the choice of reading. However, 25% of the respondents answered in the negative. They did not very much enjoy resource- based learning mentioning that they needed more guidance on what to do and how to do; they also expressed that pursuing courses through VC found tiresome and time consuming and feel drowning in a sea of information.

Jamlan (2004)

has conducted a study on "Faculty Opinions towards Introducing e-Learning at the University of Bahrain". To assess faculty opinions on e-learning, a questionnaire was sent to 30 faculty members of the University's College of Education to determine how they perceive e-learning, and how they might choose to integrate it into their everyday teaching activities. Data was collected and analyzed by using descriptive statistics. Results indicate that faculty generally perceive e-learning as a positive force in helping students' achieve their learning objectives.

Hiroshi (2005)

conducted a study titled "Questionnaire-based Evaluation of e-learning Program Operated in National Institute of Public Health" in Japan. For the sake of more development of the e-learning program in NIPH, monitoring by questionnaires of all trainees was carried out in 2005. Number of subjects posted was 298 and the valid response rate was 72%.

The results were as follows:

1. A large number of trainees were key staff engaging in the works of public health, environmental hygiene and social welfare and they pointed the advantage of the e-learning program joinable at any time and at any place;
2. Sixty percent of trainees entered the e-learning site while off duty;
3. Most of trainees learned for the purpose of improving of their own skills and not as the result of orders from their superiors;
4. They had a sufficient internet technical environment for e-learning;
5. Seventy percent of trainees who had completed at least one course of this program were satisfied with this program;
6. Though the certificate from the courses were recognized only in few workplaces, trainees could utilize their experiences from this program in their work;
7. Fifty percent of trainees advised their co-workers to apply for this program.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Data is the information collected from various sources. It is concerned with gather accurate and proper knowledge about the problem that is in hand. Formally there are 2 types of gathering information namely primary data and secondary data. Two methods have been used to collect the relevant data, which are essential for the study, they are: The collection of primary data during the course of doing experiments in an experimental research but in case we do research of the descriptive type and perform survey whether sample survey of census survey. Then we obtain primary data either through a direct communication with respondent or questionnaire. For this research secondary data was collected through various sources like, Websites, Journals, Magazines, Articles, Books and Project reports are the main sources for secondary data in this research. Population for this study is the target population like, Parents, Students and Teachers who took decision while choosing college or school.

Sampling method:

In Non-probability sampling technique the chances of selection of all elements of population are not equal and Convenience Sampling Method means sample drawn at the convenience of the interviewer people tend to makes the selection at familiar location and choose respondents who are like themselves.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Gender

2. Age

3. Occupation

4. Educational Background

5. Gender

6. Did you hear about online education before

7. What would you prefer as a mode of education

FINDINGS

- Most of people in our research are aware about online education but there are certain people who still unaware about online education.
- In our research most of people preferred mode of education is online/e-learning/virtual way and only 26% people preferred offline education.
- Most people think that online education is an effective way of learning and some people prefer offline education.

SUGGESTIONS

- Online education is a good platform for the people who are not able to complete their studies which they had left due to some reason like job timings, long distance etc.
- Online education is easy to capture and anytime, anywhere and any subject will be learning the most part of online education.
- Without physically attachment with teacher we can't learn properly. And we wanted to accept all the foreign learning styles, but we should see our resources that we have.
- Online education will help the student to learn perfectly with giving more knowledge.
- May be this way is great opportunity for those who should keep the education continue and knowledge.
- This class room environmental will help student to grow.

CONCLUSION

- The increased presence of people on internet inspire us to prepare project on online education. That is the

reason I prepared this report to check whether people are aware about online education or not.

- Throughout the report I observe that still people prefer online education because we will get ease access of information, anywhere and anytime but you won't get real time interaction like on campus study. But it has lot of advantages like, students have learn opportunity to learn while they are working.
- Most people respondents are agreed that it will improve the quality of higher education which is lack right now in the market. In our research agreed that online education gainer will get more skill than On-Campus learner.
- If we conclude full report, then we can say that online education and offline education has their own advantages and disadvantages according to the requirements of the student because some student want education while working and some students wants education full time so, both has different priorities.

References:

- [1] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education>
- [2] <https://www.kenresearch.com/education-and-recruitment/education/india-e-learning-market-research-report/393-99.html>
- [3] <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/09/is-online-learning-the-future-of-education/>
- [4] <https://www.online-education.net/articles/general/what-is-online-education.html>
- [5] <https://www.hughes.com/collateral-library/why-e-learning-has-promising-future-india>

